

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

TRANSLATION PROCEDURES OF CULTURE BOUND-TERMS (CBTs)

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Abstract

This scientific research studies culture-specific concepts (CSCS) which also include culture-bound terms (CBTs). The article aims to reveal the specific features of culture-bound terms and facilitate the translation process between TL and SL. Some procedures have been described in the article while transforming the information from one language into another. Procedures usually occur between the target language (TL) and the source language (SL). The procedure may be based on transference, naturalization, componential analysis, synonymy, shifts, modulation, compensation, paraphrasing, etc. Besides, different sets of strategies have been suggested to translate the proper names. As obvious proper names, especially human and place names remain the same while translating from source language into the target language or vice-versa. But some acronyms including organization names should be translated though they are included in proper names. Apart from cultural differences, there can be some linguistic differences between the target language and the source language that can make the translation process difficult.

Keywords: transliteration, target language, source language, interpretation, proper names, CBTs, translation

Introduction

The article studies the culture-bound terms while transforming the information from the source into the target language or vice-versa. Each nation has its specific traditions and customs. For this reason, this can induce some challenges in the translation process. There are some procedures showing the transliteration process between SL and TL. The interpreter should be professional in order to be able to translate the message from one language to another. For this reason, the author underlines: "The combination of rapidness, approximation, attention, rich vocabulary and perfect grammar knowledge makes an interpreter professional" [3, p.132]. Babayev Javid notes: "As it is a special gift given by God, sometimes to own good grammar and lexical knowledge does not solve everything" [2, p. 86]. It means that an interpreter or a translator should also possess some cultural knowledge about the target and source languages. For this reason, the author says: "Interpreter's knowledge of both native language and target language should be detailed and perfect" [1, p.51].

Main part

Graedler sets forth some procedures of translating culture-specific concepts which are as follows [5, p.3];

- a) Making up a new word
- b) Explaining the meaning of the SL expression in lieu of translating it
- c) Preservation of the SL terms intact
- d) Opting for a word in the TL which seems similar to or has the same relevance as the SL term.

Identifying culture-bound terms (CBTs) as the words that refer to the notions, personnel and institutions that are specific to the SL culture. Harvey sets forth the following 4 basic techniques for translation of CBTs: 6, p.4].

1. Functional equivalence: It means that usage of a referent in the TL culture which has an identical function equals the source language referent. As to Harvey, authors are divided over the advantages of this technique. Weston depicts it as the ideal method of interpretation while Sarcevic confirms that it is wrong and must be avoided.

2. Formal or linguistic equivalence: It is based on word for word translation.

3. Transcription or borrowing: It means reproduction or transliteration of the original term. If the term is formally transparent or explained in the context, it can be employed alone. In some cases, especially where no knowledge of the SL by the reader is assumed is observed along with an explanation or an interpreter's note.

4. Descriptive or self-explanatory translation: Generic terms are used to convey the meaning. It is relevant in a large variety of contexts while formal equivalence is thought to be obscure.

Various translation procedures proposed by Nemark are as follows:

a) transference - it is the process of transference of SL word to a TL text. It contains transliteration and it is identical to what Harvey called transcription.

b) naturalization- it matches the SL word first to the normal utterance, then to the normal morphology of the TL

c) cultural equivalent: it means a replacement of a cultural word in the SL with a TL one though they are not precise.

d) functional equivalent: it demands to use culture-neutral words.

e) descriptive equivalent: the meaning of CBT is scrutinized with some words in this procedure.

f) componential analysis: it means comparison of SL word with TL word that has identical sense but it is obscure single equivalent, showing their common meaning firstly, then their varying meaning.

g) Synonymy: it is nearly the same to target language.

h) through-translation: it is word-for-word translation of common collocations, the names of organizations or institutions and components of compound words. It may also be named calque or loan translation.

i) shifts or transportations: it covers a change in grammar from SL to TL. For example;

1. shift from singular to plural

2. shift required when a particular SL construction is not present in the TL

3. shift of the SL verb to TL word

4. shift of the SL group to a TL noun

j) modulation: it happens when the translator reproduces the information of the original text in the TL in accordance with the present norms of the TL, because the SL and the TL can appear to be different in terms of perspective.

k) recognized translation: it happens when the translator normally makes use of the official or the commonly accepted translation of any institutional term.

l) compensation: it takes place when loss of meaning in one part of the sentence is compensated in another part [51, p.90].

m) paraphrasing: the meaning of the CBT is analyzed in this procedure. Explanation here is much more detailed compared to descriptive equivalent.

n) couplets: when it happens, the translator joins two various procedures.

o) Notes: notes are supplementary data in an interpretation.

Notes can be seen in the shape of footnotes. Though some linguists consider a translation sprinkled with footnotes horrible because of appearance, nevertheless, their usage may help the TT readers to make better judgements of ST contents. Nida supports the usage of footnotes to carry out at least two functions:

1. to provide additional data

2. to call attention to the original discrepancies

A really problematic point in the translation field is considered to be the occurrence of allusions which are culture-specific portions of a SL. All sorts of allusions, particularly historical and cultural allusions, has a specific weight on the original language and should be explicated in the interpretation to set forth the richness of the SL text for the TL audience.

Being abundant in literary translations, "allusions are part of the prior cultural knowledge taken for granted by the author writing for a predominantly Moslem Arab audience. To give the closest approximation of the source language, therefore, it was necessary to opt for glossing or using explanatory footnotes" [4, p.3].

Proper names that are given by Richards as the names of a particular person, place or thing and are spelled with a capital letter play a vital role in a literary

work [11, p. 68]. They can belong to the setting, nationality of characters and social status and require focus when interpreted into a foreign language.

You can find some models to render PNs in interpretations. One of these models is introduced by Hervey and Higgins who claim that there are two strategies for translating PNs. They show that: "either the name can be taken over unchanged from the ST to the TT, or it can be adopted to conform to the phonic/graphic conventions of the TL" [7, p.29].

Hervey and Higgins call the first one exotism while they refer to the second one as transliteration: "Exotism is tantamount to literal translation and involves cultural transposition" [7, p.29].

Nevertheless, they suggest another alternative or procedure as they claim it, namely cultural transplantation. They set forth such a comparison between cultural transposition and cultural transplantation as: "extreme degree of cultural transposition, cultural transplantation is considered to be a procedure in which SL names are replaced by indigenous TL names that are not their literal equivalents but have similar cultural connotations" [7, p.29].

Considering the translation of person name, Newmark suggest that: "normally people's first and sure names are transferred thus preserving nationality and assuming that their names have no connotations in the text" [10, p.214].

Transference procedure shouldn't be considered effective where implied meanings and connotations are important. Newmark suggest a solution as: "first translate that underlies the SL proper name into the TL and naturalize the translated word back into a new SL proper name" [10, p.215].

Leppihalme suggests quite different set of strategies to translate the proper names [9]:

a) Retain the name:

1) to use the name as such

2) to use the name by adding guidance

3) to use the name by adding a detailed explanation for example a footnote.

b) Replacing the name by another:

1) to replace the name by another SL name

2) to replace the name by a TL name

c) to omit the name

1) to omit the name but the transference of the senses by other means, for example by a common noun.

2) to omit the name and the allusion together

Furthermore, 9 strategies for translation of key-phrase allusions are suggested by Leppihalme as: [9,p.82].

1. Usage of a standard translation

2. Minimum change which is a literal translation without regard to contextual meaning or connotation.

3. Extra allusive guidance added in the text

4. The use of endnotes, footnotes, interpreter's notes and other certain explanations not provided in the text but explicitly given as extra information.

5. Stimulated familiarity or internal marking, that is, the addition of intra-allusive allusion.

6. Replacement by TL item

7. to reduce the allusion to sense by rephrasing.

8. to recreate using a mix of techniques: creative construction of a text that hints at the connotation of the allusion or other special effects created by it

9. to omit the allusion

Conclusion

From the analysis of the article, it turned out that there are some procedures that help the translation process. These procedures can also be called tips or strategies of professional translation. It also became obvious that translation of proper names has different strategies. Except cultural differences, there are some grammatical differences including word order, as well. The author underlines it in his article: “subject is followed by predicate in English while the place of predicate is at the end of the sentence in the Azerbaijani language. So if the speaker speaks in Azerbaijani he will use the predicate at the end of the sentence and before that translator should approximate what verb might be used and should use that verb before the speaker utters it. The translator may guess it from the context of the speech” [8, p.117]

References:

1. Albakry, M. (2004). Linguistic and cultural issues in literary translation. Retrieved November 17, 2006
2. Babayev Javid. Significance of language skills and language aspects in sight translation. Danish

Scientific Journal. № 77, Vol 1. København V, Denmark, 2023.

3. Babayev Javid Sabir. Linguistic and cultural aspects of simultaneous translation. Publisher. agency: Proceedings of the 4th International Scientific Conference «Progress in Science» (November 9-10, 2023). Brussels, Belgium, 2023. 229 p

4. Babayev J. Impact of socio-linguistic and socio-cultural factors on translation process. Sciences of Europe. № 128, Praha, Czech Republic, 2023

5. Graedler, A.L. (2000). Cultural shock. Retrieved December 6, 2006

6. Harvey, M. (2003). A beginner's course in legal translation: the case of culture-bound terms. Retrieved April 3, 2007

7. Hervey, S., & Higgins, I. (1992). *Thinking Translation*. London & New York: Routledge.

8. Javid Babayev. Cognitive aspects of simultaneous and consecutive interpretations. Publisher. agency: Proceedings of the 1st International Scientific Conference «Interdisciplinary Science Studies» (January 19-20, 2023). Dublin, Ireland, 2023. 144p

9. Leppihalme, R. (1997). Culture bumps: an empirical approach to the translation of allusions. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters.

10. Newmark, P. (1988a). *A Textbook of Translation*. Hertfordshire: Prentice Hall.

11. Richards, et al (1985). *Longman dictionary of applied linguistics*. UK: Longman.